

ARCHITECTURAL ORGANIZATION OF PUBLIC AREAS OF RURAL POPULATION POINTS

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Abstract. *This article describes in detail the shape of public areas of rural settlements and the problems of its implementation in connection with the architectural - design organization, the location of rational public buildings based on the compositional conditions of urban planning.*

Keywords: *rational rural public centers, reclaimed land, oases, axial completion, commercial areas, adjacent quarters.*

Introduction: The government of our republic attaches great importance to the problems of radical transformation of rural areas, the development of a general service system for the rural population, and the creation of social infrastructure in the regions [1]. In order to eliminate the differences between the countryside and the city and to implement the organization of cultural and household services for the rural population, common service networks, a unified system of inter-village cultural and household service provision, and the establishment of rational rural public centers based on the conditions of compositional formation of urban development plays an important role. Public spaces are one of the architectural components that form the overall compositional solution of the village and are organized based on cultural-educational, commercial and household service buildings and are used for public events and public meetings. The important role of the fields in the organization of the architectural composition of the village requires taking into account the location of the areas in the landscape-climatic conditions when designing them.

Public spaces are the center of the architectural composition of residential areas. They are organized in the locations of the main public buildings and are used for public events and public gatherings.

The main part: 70% of the territory of our republic consists of desert, reclaimed land, oases surrounded by desert, foothill valleys, hills, and mountains [3].

The main part of the population lives in irrigated and agricultural zones. The developed and more developed areas of the cities are located in the eastern part of our republic, the less developed areas are located in the newly irrigated lands, in the Kizil Kum and Karshi deserts. Depending on the zone of the settlement, the areas of public centers can be divided into closed, semi-open and open spatial compositions. The design of fields can be in several compositional directions. The direction of axial completion allows creating architectural ensembles characterized by a high level of open spatial order, clarity and logic.

The formation of fields according to the common compositional direction divides objects into groups according to the size of the field. Their main features are the absence of intersecting perspectives, integrity, undividedness of the main area, forming a closed composition by organizing corridors in all directions.

The area of settlements refers to the spatial solution of extended streets designed for special purposes.

Picture-1 The area of the community center of settlements. *a-closed tubes, b-opened in water bodies.*

According to their function, the fields can be divided into 4 main groups: 1) public; 2) transport; 3) unloading; 4) commercial areas.

Transport areas serve to better organize movement at street intersections. Transports are designed in front of the entrance to the fields, clubs, stadiums, parks to facilitate unloading.

Trade areas serve to organize markets, fairs and are designed in front of commercial buildings.

Each rural area that is designed in residential areas must fulfill a specific task. In practice, in the design and construction of rural settlements, it is accepted to organize one area that performs more public functions. Such an area will be established at the location of the community center and will be called the community center area. In large villages, several community centers can be organized, one main and the rest subordinate to it.

The area of residential areas is formed at the expense of the intersection of the blocks in the corner of the construction area on the streets or by their expansion on one or both sides in one part of the street, at the same time at the expense of the adjacent quarters.

Picture-2. Kashkadarya region, Kasbi district "Yuksalish" QFY. *a – current state plan; b - a proposal for residential buildings and a community center organized along the road.*

Areas of community centers can be organized by any of the methods discussed above. The first option is more appropriate for transport areas, and the second option is more appropriate for the unloading area. It is necessary to pay special attention to the design of the areas of public

centers, because they are the compositional center of residential areas. These areas should have expressive architecture, and at the same time form a luxurious, memorable ensemble.

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The shape of the square plan, its dimensions, are solved in a harmonious unit with respect to the streets adjacent to it, and at the same time, the placement of buildings, plants, components of other architectural spatial content on the square, as well as with the general design condition of the residential area in organic connection, they are solved together (1, 2 - picture).

The shape of the field has different geometric shapes in the plan. The most rational form can be shown in the plan of the public center square, which is slightly extended, with sides 2:3 - 1:2; around these dimensions, the classic ratio "golden section" is 1:1.62. The right quadrilaterals will be in a clear direction, which is important for the growing, community center area.

Trapezoidal areas will have a clearly expressed direction due to the expansion of their sides. Equilateral proportions indicate construction along symmetry, and right quadrilaterals indicate construction without symmetry. The architectural form of the square is a three-dimensional, fully or partially enclosed, architecturally organized spatial environment. It is firmly connected with buildings, other structures, landscaped plants, etc. It is these volumetric elements that create an architecturally organized field space.

Squares are considered the center of architectural composition of residential areas and are of great importance in its overall location. Therefore, designing the area of public centers is one of the main tasks, and it is the formation of their main architectural ensemble. The unity of the area is achieved through the exact proportionality of its shapes and sizes, which decorate the buildings as an architectural – spatial ensemble. One of the main ways to achieve such a unity is the mutual agreement of the axis of buildings and the axis of the area.

The symmetrical axis of the buildings to be built around the square should be coordinated and compatible with the axis of the square and the axis of the streets connecting to it. The integrity of the architectural-design composition will look better if all axes are subordinate to the symmetrical axis of the main building, and this symmetrical axis is coordinated with the compositional plan of the main street and the location of residential areas (3 - picture).

Picture-3. The axis of the main building in the community center is subordinated to the square. 1st House of Culture; 2nd administrative building with agrolaboratory; 3rd village council; 4-universal magazine; 5-store kitchen; 6.7 residential buildings; 8th main street.

In this case, the axis of the main building of the square should be the main organizer in the complete design and construction of the square.

The axis of the main building should be subordinated to the entire area, otherwise, even if there are several mutually agreed axes, the unity of the architectural composition may be lost.

The architectural organization of the public center of the square is carried out in each specific case, taking into account all the possibilities of the composition and using the conditions and features of the place, as well as natural and national traditions (Fig. 4).

Conclusion: In conclusion, public center areas are considered the center of architectural composition of residential areas and are of great importance in its overall location. Therefore, designing the area of public centers is one of the main tasks, and it is the formation of their main architectural ensemble. The area of the village community center, as the main element of its architecture-design composition, should give the population area an individuality and a unique appearance.

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